

CYBER CRIME, THREAT
AND
SECURITY
SURVEY REPORT

Conducted for
Threat Intelligence Platform project

By
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December 2017

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INTRODUCTION

In the last several years, there has been a disturbing trend in cyber security with attackers innovating much faster than defenders do. We've seen commercialization of malware, with attack kits available on underground forums for anyone who wants to perpetrate a variety of attacks. Large **botnets** are available for rent, allowing attackers to send spam or launch **DDoS** attacks at will. Many attackers use malware to command and control protocols and methods, adapting to their products over time to keep a head of the anti-malware industry and security professionals. As more and more attacks occur, however, the likelihood increases that some organizations or groups have seen the attack before.

The idea behind **TIP** is to leverage intelligence feeds provided by **CTI** to provide the ability to recognize and act upon indicators of attack and compromise scenarios in a timely manner.

There is a lot of confusion about what threat intelligence is and how it's delivered and consumed. This survey has been carried out to collect pieces of data from various stakeholders to come up with a detailed report on cyber threat and security.

About the survey

This survey aims at forming a more comprehensive understanding of how cyber incidents are affecting businesses.

It aims to gain a picture of the

- Business – general description.
- Current cyber security measures in place.
- Recent cyber security incidents identified, and.
- Reporting of cyber security incidents.

Additional questions were included in this survey to gain a more comprehensive understanding of each of the above categories. Further, the survey seeks to understand business concerns about cyber threats.

The survey was produced and conducted by BEAR Team. It consisted of 34 questions, both closed and open ended.

To ensure that the most accurate and informed responses were obtained, questions were asked to be completed by the Chief Information Officer and/or an IT security officer in each organization. Respondents were assured that all answers are anonymous.

Summary of Key Findings

Findings from the survey reveal a range of concerns and potential vulnerabilities.

- 61% of organizations do not have cyber security incidents identified in their risk register.
- 13% of organizations using Windows XP did not have plans to migrate to other software.
- only 27% of organizations had increased expenditure on IT security in the previous 12 months.
- 16% of organizations have no staff dedicated to IT security, and the majority (72%) of large organizations (200+ employees) only have small IT security areas (1-5 full time staff).
- 42% of organizations with a physical presence in other countries do not consider the internationally connected networks within their organizational IT security posture.

Areas for improvement have also been identified.

- 95% of respondents think general staff need to improve their IT security skills and/or practices.
- 91% of respondents think management need to improve their IT security skills and/or practices.
- More than 60% of respondents think IT staff, the CEO and the board of directors need to improve their IT security skills and/or practices.
- The main internal factors that contributed to cyber security incidents were staff errors and/or omissions (57%) and poor security culture (50%).

- The main external factors that contributed to cyber security incidents were targeted attack (51%) and third party risks and/or vulnerabilities (49%).

RESULTS

1. Respondents

Industry sector

Responses were received from 5 organizations, from more than 12 industry sectors. The greatest representation was from defence (24%), followed by energy (16%), banking and finance (13%), government (12%), and other (11%).

Note : ‘defence’ refers to defence contractors or members of the army, ‘government’ refers mostly to government-business enterprises (ie critical infrastructure) and ‘other’ includes businesses in legal services, gaming/media and entertainment, and software development.

Figure 1: Breakdown of sectors that responded to survey

2. Cyber security measures

Cyber security involves the prevention and detection of the unauthorized access, use or impairment of an organization’s network data or systems.

To maximize cyber resilience, modern organization’s layer security defences for their IT systems reduce the chance of a successful attack. This concept is known as defence-in-depth and seeks to manage risk with multiple defensive

strategies, so that if one layer of defence turns out to be inadequate, another layer will hopefully prevent a full breach. The multiple defence mechanisms layered across an organization’s network infrastructure protect data, networks, and users. A well-designed and implemented defence-in-depth strategy can help system administrators identify internal and external attacks on a computer system or network.

IT security area

Results indicate that 84% of responding organizations have IT security areas. Of those, 89% have internal IT security teams, and 11% outsource their IT security.

Whether internal or outsourced, 74% of the IT security areas are reportedly small (1 -5 full time equivalent staff), 5% are medium (5 – 15 full time equivalent staff) and 5% are large (15+ full time equivalent staff). Of concern, 16% of respondents reported their organization did not have an IT security area – with no staff dedicated to this role. Also of note, most of the large organizations (72%) have small IT security areas.

International presence

Findings indicate that 65% of responding organizations are based solely in Uganda, while 35% have a physical presence in other countries. Of those with a physical presence in other countries, 42% do not consider the internationally connected networks as part of their IT security posture.

This finding is of concern, as all organizations with a physical presence and IT network in other countries need to consider internationally connected networks as part of their IT security posture.

IT security policies

Organizations were asked what type of IT security policies they use.

Results indicate that basic security policies are being applied by the majority of surveyed organizations. For example, 94% deploy user access management, 90% have business continuity/disaster recovery plans, 87% use

change control, 82% have automated system backups, 81% have documented standard operating procedures, and 81% have an incident management or response plan.

While the majority of organizations report they have these security policies, there are also areas for improvement. For example, less than 60% of respondents use cryptographic controls, and around 50% of respondents have plans in place for the management of removable computer media, such as USB memory drives.

In addition, only 25% of respondents reported having a forensic investigation plan. These plans help monitor the use of the IT systems, provide mechanisms to recover lost data, and provide ways to protect information on systems.

Figure 2: breakdown of security policies being used by responding organizations

IT security standards

When asked if their organization uses external IT security standards or frameworks.

- 83% of respondents reported ‘yes’.
- 13% of respondents reported ‘no’.
- 4% of respondents reported they ‘did not know’.

Risk register

When asked if the threat factor of cyber security incidents had been identified in their organization’s risk register

- 39% of respondents reported ‘yes’.
- 61% of respondents reported ‘no’.

This finding is of concern and indicates an area for improvement, as all organizations should factor the risk of a cyber security incident into their business continuity planning.

A risk register is used to record any and all identified risks, as well as incidents and analysis of mitigation plans. This provides IT security teams with a better understanding of the threat landscape, so they can develop stronger mitigation strategies to protect their systems.

Management within organizations also need to ensure that, to be truly resilient in relation to the spectrum of risks that could affect their organization, cyber security incidents have been factored into the risk register, and appropriate measures are taken to mitigate those risks.

IT security technologies

Organizations were asked what type of IT security technologies they use.

More than 90% of respondents reported using anti-spam filters, anti-virus software, traditional firewalls (network based), physical access control, email attachment filtering, remote access VPNs, and operating system patch management.

More than 80% reported using password complexity rules, digital certificates, and web filtering/content inspection.

Figure 3: IT security technologies being used by responding organizations

More than 70% reported using privileged account restrictions, and application patch management. More than 60% also reported using internal network segregation, multi-factor authentication (such as smart cards, tokens, biometrics), and traditional firewalls (host based). Only 30% of respondents reported using application white-listing (one of the Top 4 mitigation strategies).

IT security skills and training

Respondents were asked about the IT security training and qualifications of the IT security staff in their organization. Responses indicate that 79% of organizations have IT security staff with at least five years experience working in IT security. More than 65% of organizations have IT security staff with tertiary level IT qualifications.

Around 60% of organizations have IT security staff with either vendor certifications, vendor neutral certifications or who have participated in ad-hoc courses.

Findings indicate that 7% of organizations have IT security staff with no form of IT security training or qualification.

Respondents were also asked if other staff in their organization need to improve their IT security skills and/or practices.

- 95% of respondents reported this need for general staff.
- 91% of respondents reported this need for management.
- 66% of respondents reported this need for IT staff.
- 63% of respondents reported this need for the CEO.
- 62% of respondents reported this need for the board of directors.

IT security expenditure

When asked if their organization had increased expenditure on IT security in the previous 12 months.

- 73% of respondents reported 'no'.
- 27% of respondents reported 'yes'.

Of those organizations that had increased expenditure on IT security, the majority was on technical security controls (87%), followed by risk assessments (56%). Expenditure was also made on IT security training (38%), consultants (38%) and additional IT security staff (13%).

Figure 4: breakdown of expenditure on IT security

Windows XP – end of life

When asked if their organization uses Windows XP.

- 47% of respondents reported 'yes'.
- 52% of respondents reported 'no'.
- 1% of respondents reported 'don't know'.

When asked if their organization is aware that technical assistance for Windows XP is no longer available since April 2014

- 97% of respondents reported 'yes'.
- 2% of respondents reported 'no'.
- 1% of respondents reported 'don't know'.

Of the organizations using Windows XP, the majority (79%) had planned to migrate to other software before April 2014.

8% didn't know if their organization has such IT security plans in place. Organizations that still use Windows XP are at an increased risk of network vulnerability and compromise, as the software is no longer being supported or patched.

3. Cyber security incidents

Respondents were asked about the number and type of cyber security incidents identified on their networks in the previous 12 months.

Respondents were also asked about the origin and possible motives for the attacks, as well as why the attacks may have been successful.

Cyber security incidents were considered to be those that harmed the confidentiality, integrity or availability of a network’s data or systems.

Number of incidents

Respondents were asked if any cyber security incidents had been identified on their networks in the previous 12 months.

Results indicate that 56% of organizations did identify one or more cyber security incident in the previous 12 months, while 44% did not.

This finding may reflect that a number of cyber intrusions have gone undetected by some organizations, or that their definition of an incident is different. Anecdotal evidence available to the CERT suggests that some businesses are unaware of the full scope of unauthorized activity on their networks.

Figure 5: number of cyber security incidents identified by organizations in the previous 12 months.

Types of incidents

Of the respondents who reported their organization had identified cyber security incidents in the previous 12 months, they assessed the main types were

- 63% - targeted emails.
- 52% - virus or worm infection.
- 46% - trojan or rootkit malware.
- 35% - theft of mobile devices.
- 26% - unauthorized access.
- 17% - ransom-ware.
- 17% - distributed denial of service.
- 17% - unauthorized access to information from an insider.

These findings may help organizations decide where to place additional resources to protect their information assets.

Interestingly, the main incident identified was targeted emails. These are socially engineered emails that are designed to assist an adversary in gaining a foothold on a network undetected, to extract valuable company or client information.

Such ‘spear phishing’ emails appear to be from a known source – but the links and attached files are designed to by-pass security and create an entry point onto a network. This method is particularly effective in organizations where cyber resilience is not part of the culture providing a timely reminder that all staff have a role to play in cyber security. Also of interest and concern is that there were no reports of mobile devices being compromised yet.

Figure 6: breakdown of the type of cyber security incidents

Apparent motives of incidents

Attribution is always difficult. Where respondents think an attack may have come from, may not be where it actually originated.

Many respondents indicated they did not know the origin of the cyber security incidents experienced. Others attributed the incidents to internal factors such as staff errors and/or omissions and a poor security culture, as well as external factors such as targeted emails. Respondents who reported their organization had experienced cyber security incidents in the

previous 12 months were asked about the apparent motives or reasons for the attacks.

In priority order, the main apparent motives were :-

- Competitor seeking commercial advantage.
- Malicious damage.
- Using the system for further attacks.
- Personal grievance.
- Issue motivated/Hackers.
- Other (including carelessness, lack of attention and negligence).
- Don't know.
- Illicit financial gain.
- Random or indiscriminate.

The main motive for attack – a competitor seeking commercial advantage – relates to the theft of intellectual property. There are a range of actors involved in this form of cyber crime – some benefit directly, while others sell the information.

Whatever the motive or reason for a cyber attack, it is important that an organization understands enough about the incident to determine the vulnerabilities on their network, what data may have been accessed, and what needs to be done to increase the protections of their network.

Figure 7: Apparent motives for cyber security incidents

Contributing factors to the incidents

Respondents were asked what internal factors may have contributed to the cyber security incidents identified by their organization in the previous 12 months.

The main factors were staff errors and/or omissions (57%), followed by poor security

culture (50%), unpatched or unprotected software (48%) and misconfigured systems, applications or network devices (48%).

Lack of technical security controls (41%) and lack of IT security staff (22%) were also considered to be contributing factors.

Figure 8: internal factors contributing to cyber security incidents

Respondents were also asked what external factors may have contributed to the cyber security incidents experienced by their organization in the previous 12 months.

The main factors were targeted attack (51%), followed by third party risks and/or vulnerabilities (49%), sophisticated attackers (38%), powerful automated attack tools (36%) and volume of attacks (31%).

Figure 9: external factors contributing to cyber security incidents

4. Reporting cyber security incidents

Respondents who stated their organization had experienced cyber security incidents in the previous 12 months (56% of responding

organizations) were asked about reporting the incident

Reporting of incidents and to whom

Respondents were asked if the cyber security incidents had been reported and if so, to whom.

Results indicate that 57% of respondents did not report cyber security incidents to any outside agency, and 9% did not know if the incidents were reported.

The remaining respondents (34%) did report cyber security incidents to either UCC and/or as mandatory reporting to a regulator, and/or to law enforcement.

Reasons for not reporting

Respondents who did not report cyber security incidents were asked why. The main reasons were:-

- 44% - 'there are no benefits of reporting'.
- 44% - 'other'.
- 20% - 'the attackers probably wouldn't get caught &/or prosecuted'.
- 16% - 'did not know'.
- 12% - 'negative publicity for the organization'.

'Other' reasons for not reporting included that the incidents and the consequences were minor, and that the incidents were reported internally and managed by corporate policy.

5. Concerns about and responses to cyber threats

All respondents were asked a series of questions about the cyber actors and threats of most concern to their organization, and the responses to cyber threats they consider most important.

This information aims to ascertain areas of future concern, to assist with understanding the trending of cyber security incidents.

Cyber actors of most concern

In terms of their organization, respondents were asked which cyber actors concern them the most.

These are not necessarily the actors that have been involved in previous cyber security incidents but are of future concern to organizations.

The main actors are

- 59% - issue motivated groups or Hackers.
- 54% - organized criminal syndicates.
- 52% - trusted insiders.
- 43% - individuals.
- 42% - the intelligence services of some foreign governments.
- 6% - other (included business competitors and disgruntled employees).

These findings indicate that issue motivated groups or Hackers are of most concern. If targeting critical infrastructure, these actors could cause significant harm and disruption, not only to the organization but to the broader social and economic well being of the nation.

While traditional attacks by this category of cyber actors has involved defacement and distributed denial of service attacks, more recent activity has also involved domain name system (DNS) redirection.

Organized criminal syndicates and trusted insiders also rated highly as cyber actors of concern.

Figure 10: breakdown of cyber actors of most concern

Cyber threats of most concern

In terms of their organization, respondents were asked which cyber threats concern them the most. The main threats are theft or breach of confidential information (68%), unauthorized access (67%), unauthorized access to information

from an outsider (65%) and unauthorized access to information from an insider (51%).

These threats are followed by theft or loss of intellectual property (48%), Trojan or root-kit malware (47%), targeted emails (46%), unauthorized data modification (46%), virus or worm infection (43%) and theft of mobile devices (36%).

These findings indicate a range of cyber threats that are of concern to organizations. Theft or breach of confidential information and unauthorized access to information from both insiders and outsider appear to be of most concern.

Interestingly, targeted emails are of concern although perhaps not to the extent they should be, as findings from this survey indicate this was the main type of cyber security incident experienced by organizations. A successful targeted email is often the precursor to theft or breach of confidential information and a number of other listed consequences of cyber threats.

Figure 11: breakdown of cyber threats of most concern

Vulnerable parts of organizations

Respondents were asked which parts of their organization are most vulnerable to cyber threats. The main vulnerability reported is the internal network (51%), followed by externally facing systems (45%), public website (43%), mobile devices being compromised (35%), remote access (34%), mobile devices being stolen (34%) and gateway environment (31%).

These vulnerabilities were followed by concerns about vulnerabilities in supervisory control and data acquisition systems (SCADA) (23%), partner networks (22%) and cloud (22%). Findings indicate that protecting an organization’s internal network, or methods of accessing that network is of paramount importance to the majority of respondents.

An internal network may have a range of system vulnerabilities, such as weaknesses in authentication, unused and unpatched services, as well as insecure routers and switches – all of which make it easier for unauthorized access to the network. If cyber criminals do gain access to a network, it is open for exploitation. This aligns with the finding that targeted emails, or ‘spear phishing’, were the main cyber incidents experienced by organizations.

Interestingly, mobile devices being compromised is considered a vulnerability. This is inconsistent with the earlier finding, which indicates organizations did not experience this type of cyber security incident refer to figure 6 (0% of mobile devices being compromised).

The findings also indicate that organizations have a range of cyber security vulnerabilities, highlighting the need for comprehensive cyber security and risk management plans and procedures.

For example, while the vulnerability of SCADA systems was considered to be relatively low, the consequences of a compromise to these and other industrial control systems may be severe over and above that of other compromises. SCADA systems are used in much of the critical infrastructure that underpins essential services, such as those delivered by the water, electricity, communications, gas and transport sectors. They also perform major roles in the manufacturing and resource sectors.

Figure 12: Parts of organizations most vulnerable to cyber threats

The most important responses to cyber threats

Respondents were asked what they thought were the most important responses to cyber threats.

The main responses were senior leadership support (76%), training (72%), technical controls (64%), culture change (59%) and procedural controls (53%). These were followed by intelligence sharing (50%), risk management processes (48%) and industry collaboration (39%). These findings indicate that an organization's social and behavioural responses, as well as technical responses are important for cyber security. Of note, senior leadership support, training and culture change were identified as priorities.

Methodology

1. Sample

The universe for this study is all adults 18 and older in the continental Africa and country Uganda working in the field of networks and communication.

The sample was selected in two stages. In the first stage, the sampling frame was a list of randomly selected organizations.

The second stage of sampling was selection at the organization level. All organizations where there was some IT infrastructure however small it was,

were reached, the survey respondents were selected using a random probability method, i.e. interviewers requested to speak with the IT personnel in the organization who was present at the time. All sample surveys are subject to possible sampling error; that is, the results may differ from those which would be obtained if the entire population under study were interviewed. The margin of sampling error for the entire survey is plus or minus 2.5 percentage points at the 95% level of confidence. This means that in 95 out of 100 samples of this size the results obtained in the sample would fall in a range of plus or minus 2.5 percentage points of what would have been obtained if every individual had been interviewed. Other non-sampling error may also contribute to total survey error.

2. Questionnaire and Interviewing

The questionnaire used in this study was designed by Bear Team as well as numerous other software engineering members.

A draft of the questionnaire was subjected to a pretest, resulting in modifications to the questionnaire both in terms of question wording and length. The fieldwork was conducted both in person and by telephone using a computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CATI) system, in November, 2017 by a team of professional Engineers, fully trained and supervised. A briefing session familiarized the interviewers with the sample specifications and the instrument for this study. The interviews averaged 20 minutes in length. Bear Team monitored the interviewing and data collection at all stages to ensure quality.

3. Data Analysis

The demographic characteristics of the sample, obtained via the selection methods described above, were matched to Census population estimates for Uganda. The data collected have been weighted statistically to bring age and race into their proper proportions for the population.

Conclusion

Network Security is likely here to stay and is growing more mature and important. More tools are integrating CTI feeds and data, and teams are currently seeing improvements in detection and response capabilities as a result. However most of the tools already in place are less reliable and too complicated to use by a number of stake holders.

Many survey respondents provided general comments and suggestions on what they feel is needed to improve the network security and make it more impactful now and ever. The majority of comments focused on automation, better real-time intelligence, and improved vetting and accuracy of intelligence data. Numerous respondents mentioned improvements in standards and tools that can collect, digest and integrate cyber crime. Watch for rapid advancements from vendors and the security community alike.

A number of the respondents suggested that the tools should reflect the nature of the market (Ugandan market) in which they will be deployed and probably this will improve usability of the tools being used here in Uganda.